

PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES OF PERSONAL CREATIVITY

Kadyrova Gulnora Khasanovna

Docent of the department of the Institute of Pedagogical Innovations,
Vocational System Management and Retraining of Pedagogical
Personnel and their Qualification, Doctor of Philosophy of Pedagogical
Sciences (PhD)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7132504>

Abstract: At any time, the development of the field of education is directly combined with the creativity of the participants of the educational process. In education, issues of personal creativity are considered as one of the important factors of personal development. This article tells about the essence of the concept of "creativity" in education and the pedagogical opportunities of the student's creative self-development.

Key words and concepts: creativity in the educational process, individual creativity, motivational environment, differential approach.

Аннотация: Ҳар қайси замон таълим соҳасининг ривожланиши бевосита таълим жараёни иштирокчиларининг ижодкорлиги билан уйғунлашган. Таълимда шахс ижодкорлиги масалаларига шахсий ривожланишининг муҳим омилларидан бири сифатида қаралади. Ушбу мақолада таълимда "ижодкорлик" тушунчасининг моҳияти ҳамда таълим олувчининг ижодий ўзини ўзи ривожлантиришидаги педагогик имкониятлар ҳақида сўз боради..

Таянч сўз ва тушунчалар: таълим жараёнида ижодкорлик, шахс ижодкорлиги, мотивацион муҳит, дифференциал ёндашув.

Аннотация: Во все времена развитие сферы образования напрямую сочеталось с творчеством участников образовательного процесса. В образовании вопросы личностного творчества рассматриваются как один из важных факторов развития личности. В данной статье говорится о сущности понятия «творчество» в образовании и о педагогических возможностях творческого саморазвития учащегося.

Ключевые слова и понятия: творчество в образовательном процессе, творчество личности, мотивационная среда, дифференцированный подход.

The concept of "creativity" is interpreted in different fields as qualities close in content, but different in form. In its general form, it is the creation of new, original, more developed material and spiritual values of objective or subjective value.

In philosophy, creativity is understood as a spiritual and practical activity, the product of which is the creation of unique, cultural, and socially significant values; the discovery of new facts, the discovery of new properties and laws, as well as ways of exploring and changing the world are counted. This position "if the fundamental creative relation of the subject to the world and to himself is truly accepted, then it involves the addition or completion of a new, unprecedented result in relation to existence (and knowledge)".[1]

Research scientist G. Ibragimova put forward the opinion that "...personal creativity is a process directly related to the individual-psychological characteristics of a person. Its development is influenced by the process of intellect-intuition-logical thinking". [5].

Pedagogical researchers consider the creativity of the teacher and the learner as an important

aspect of the educational process.

In the research work of A.V. Khutorsky [9], pedagogical creativity is defined as follows:

- one of the approaches to understanding a person and his essence, in which the essence of a person (his thinking as a threefold intuitive-conceptual-emotional nature) is understood through self-awareness of spiritual, intellectual and vital abilities for creative activity (in literature - creative). The self-awareness of creativity is aimed at the development of the outside world, and the individual is the subject of self-development, his ability to think, choose and recognize, and indirectly plays the role of developing society;
- the ability of spiritual and creative thinking, which allows to create unusual ideas, to deviate from the traditional, algorithmic aspects of thinking, to find solutions to problematic situations;
- the ability to create original intellectual products, including in pedagogical activities; it is the self-awareness of integrity and pedagogical consciousness and the direction of individual pedagogical thinking when the person of the information society acts as a subject of self-development at all age levels of leading (main) activity.

From a social and historical point of view, creativity appears as a process that occurs in a person at a certain time or depends on social relations, as criteria for evaluating creative products.

Creativity in various literatures:

- as an intellectual ability to "produce" unusual ideas, move away from traditional boundaries and quickly solve problematic situations [4];
- as "an ability that can manifest itself in the types of thinking, feeling, communication, individual activities, can manifest the person as a whole and its separate aspects, the products of activity, the process of their creation";
- creativity is considered as a psychological theory.

The science of general pedagogy defines the concept of "creativity" as "an ability that reflects the ability of a person to create new concepts and form new skills", in other words, the ability to be creative, "as a readiness to use and develop one's own abilities", "a necessary search-transformation attitude of a person" to search for oneself- is manifested in the transformation activity" [3]. As a result of the analysis of the literature, we came across different opinions and approaches about the creativity of the individual. In any approach, the unique nature of creativity is emphasized. For example, the ability to get out of a certain situation, to set a goal. Below we have presented the opinions of some researchers-scientists within the framework of the concept of individual creativity.

Views on the concept of "personal creativity"

No	"Personal creativity" concepts
1.	The highest qualities characteristic of a perfect person are creativity, ability, love of science. (A. Navoi) [5]
2.	Pedagogical scientists define the concept of "personal creativity" as follows: A sense of openness to progress and news; this is a high level of thinking, its flexibility, uncompromisingness and originality, the ability to quickly change the methods of action in accordance with new conditions of activity. (Y.N. Glukhova)[2]
3.	A system of personal abilities (ingenuity, imagination, critical thinking, openness

	to new information) that allows optimizing the methods of actions in accordance with new conditions, and knowledge, skills, belief systems, performance of activities that determine the results of actions (innovation, originality, originality of approaches), the individual is the result of encouraging creative self-awareness and self-development. (V.G. Ryndak) [8]
4.	The superiority of the process of creating a new one (A.V. Brushlinsky, V.A. Molyako, V.N. Pushkin) [5]
5.	Social-psychological approach to non-traditional resolution of conflicts of objective reality. (E.V. Kashapova) [6]
6.	A holistic personal characteristic expressed in a person's attitude to creativity (setting, position, orientation). (Mamykin I) [7]

Despite the certain similarity and closeness of the concepts of "creativity" and "creativity", they are not the same. To distinguish between these concepts, researchers of the psychology of creativity recommend using two characteristics: process-based (to show creativity) and subjective-conditional (to show creativeness). Consequently, creativity is something that is carried out by a person with a certain characteristic and leads to the creation of a new one, and creativeness it is understood as a process that is the source of a person's internal potential.

The content of creative education is formed at three levels: general, theoretical expression, academic subject educational materials. Among these levels of formation, we will focus on the importance of educational materials.

Educational material, both didactically and psychologically, in a general form, educational material mediates the transfer of educational content from the level of normative social knowledge and experience to the level of individual learning. Its purpose is to build public knowledge and experiences for every learner.

In addition, it serves in the activities of teachers and learners, that is, in the process of solving problems. Traditionally, educational materials are structured in such a way as to ensure the acquisition of knowledge and skills. However, modern conditions demand from a person not only the acquisition of knowledge, but also the ability to transfer it from one area of knowledge to another, the ability to think, argue, prove one's point of view, and put forward hypotheses.

Educational research activity is a tool that informs the student about scientific methods of learning. By mastering the existing elements of these methods, students acquire the skills of independently acquiring new knowledge, planning a search, and discovering new relationships and patterns. Unlike scientific research, the main goal of research activity is to seek to change reality by obtaining new knowledge about the subject of study. Educational research aims to change the learner himself by creating qualitatively new values.

The main criterion of personal creativity in education is the development of the learner's personality. In this, he sets the task of having several indicators within the framework of the professional training of the educator:

- The ability to see the individual characteristics of learners and conduct training in accordance with the individual characteristics of each of them;
- forms of reflection and self-awareness;

- ability to change lesson goals in accordance with changing reality; to be able to see the manifestation of discoveries and other aspects of learners, to be able to help their development;
- the ability to organize various forms of organization of individual creative works of students and their protection measures;
- to be able to prepare a qualitative description of the student's changes in education, to evaluate the diversity of the development of his personal qualities;
- to achieve personal creative growth;
- to be able to feel the meaning and goals of the educational activity according to the educational subject or types of activities, to be able to connect them with the creative self-awareness and creative self-development of the natural opportunities of the learners; to be able to have one's own educational position, who knows how to set educational goals in the educational topic, how to achieve them during the teaching process and clearly define them;
- is able to create an integrated curriculum that takes into account educational standards and pedagogical instructions; to be able to correlate reality with the structured program, to be able to organize the educational process.

The formation of the above indicators allows the modern teacher to organize the lesson at a creative level.

The creative level lesson is one of the forms of organizing the educational process that ensures the formation of the creative thinking of students and the development of their creative abilities. Forms a system of motives and personal characteristics (independence, motivation for self-expression); turns general ability into active creativity. This lesson covers the entire teaching system of the teacher (content, purpose, tasks, fundamental educational objects and problems, types of student activities, expected results, reflection and results evaluation forms), as well as modern educational technologies of teaching (modular teaching technology, creative teaching technology), education is a lesson that reflects the recipient's knowledge of organizing independent work (creative technologies, research technologies, etc.), creative methods, styles, and forms.

Thus, the potential of the learner in creative self-development was manifested as a set of opportunities that develop in the methods, forms, tools and knowledge of the creative level lesson, which allows taking into account the interests of the learner. It should be noted that the results of increasing the level of creativity in the teacher lead to emotional and personal changes in the learners.

References:

1. Aripdzhanova A.R. Razvitiya kreativnogo potentsiala pedagogov vysshikh obrazovatelnykh uchrejdeniy v usloviyax informatizatsii obrazovaniya. Doctoral dissertation. T. 2017
2. Glukhova A.Yu. Attestatsionno pedagogicheski complex razvitiya creativity studentov v protesse professionalnoy podgotovki: Abstract cand. ped. sciences. - Magnitogorsk. - 2006. - 26 p.
3. Gorbatov, D.S. Umeniya i navyki: o sootnoshenii sodержaniya etikh ponyatiy / D.S. Gorbatov // Pedagogika. 1994. No. 2. p. 15-19;

4. Duranov, M.E. Pedagogika and psixologiya,: study guide / M.E. Duranov, Tretyakova T.N., T.V. Galkina. - Chelyabinsk: YuUrGU; 2000. — 98 p.
5. Ibragimova G.N. Interfaol ukitysh metodlari va tekhnologiyalari asosida talabalarning kreativlik kobilyatlarini rivojlantirish.. Candidate work. T. 2017
6. Kashapova M.M., Assoc. T.G. Kiseleva, Assoc. T.V. Ogorodova. Kreativnost kak klyuchevaya kompetentnost pedagoga: Monograph. Under the editorship prof. Yaroslavl: IPK "Indigo". -2013. - 392 p.
7. Mamykin I. Naputi k kreativnomu obucheniyu: voprosy metodologii i metodiki // Filosofskie traditsii i sovremennost. - 2015. - No. 2(8). - P.97-103. URL: <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=25447757> .
8. Ryndak, V.G. Shkola: s vekom naravne: monograph / V.G. Ryndak. - Orenburg: Publishing house OGPU, 2010. - 220 p.
9. Khutorskoy, A.V. Klyuchevye kompetentsii. Tekhnologiya konstruirovaniya/ A.V. Khutorskoy // Narodnoe obrazovanie. - 2003. - No. 5. - p. 55-61.